

Title: Improved Thermal Comfort of Light Weight Structure with Macro-Encapsulated PCM

R Stropnik, E Zavrl and U Stritih

University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Ljubljana, Slovenia
rok.stropnik@fs.uni-lj.si

Abstract. Thermally well-insulated lightweight framed buildings prevent heat losses through their envelope and reduce the energy demand over the heating season. However, the heat capacity of the lightweight wall is relatively low and in summer, building lacks thermal stability and overheats. Since the overheating of modern lightweight prefabricated structures is an increasingly common problem on a global scale, the macro-encapsulated PCM is one of a possible solution for improving thermal comfort and decreasing energy demand for cooling. The analysis of operation temperatures for lightweight structure with and without PCM for three geographical locations was made. Furthermore, energy demand for cooling is calculated for each location and compared. The results show that lightweight structure with PCM, 24 °C melting point, improved thermal comfort and decrease cooling demand for all locations.

1. Introduction

European project named Holistic Energy and Architectural Retrofit Toolkit (HEART) focuses on the renovation of residential buildings by merging the following technologies as one renovation concept: Cloud-based platform for decision support and building energy management, smart DC fan-coils, Multi-input/Multi-output power controller, hydronic modular DC heat pump, battery pack, high efficiency water storage tank, universal BIPV tiles, multifunctional external thermal insulation system and replacement techniques and/or components of existing windows [1].

In accordance with the requirements of EU Regulation on construction products [2], lightweight structures as a part of building envelope system are described as “structural loadbearing elements, which have to enable the required mechanical stability, at lower weight than it is generally achievable by other heavyweight building structures”. EU Regulation can be reached either by decreasing the amount of material used for structure or by using higher rate of functionality within the lightweight

structure [3], [4]. The lightweight framed buildings (hereinafter lightweight buildings) are gaining in popularity in current construction and renovation, mainly due to shorter construction time, lower construction expenses and minimised environmental impact with higher reuse potential [5], [6]. To control and prevent heat, water and sound transfer, protective layers - constructional products are added, in a function of thermal and sound insulations, waterproofing membrane, vapour barrier, etc. Additionally, lightweight construction is stimulated in many international and national policies and strategies based on lowering the climate change [7] to be in line with the Kyoto protocol.

Beside economic and environmental advantages, their weakness compared to heavyweight buildings is related to the performance and mutual relation to energy consumption and comfort. Thermally well insulated lightweight framed buildings prevent heat losses through their envelope and perform well when reducing the energy demand over the heating season. However, the heat capacity and thermal insulation of the lightweight wall is relatively low. Thus, in summer time, it cannot accumulate the environmental heat. As a consequence, the building lacks thermal stability and its interior overheats [8]. This results in deteriorated thermal comfort over the summer time, also known as overheating.

Overheating mainly occurs due to low accumulation capabilities in dwellings, across the entire Europe, even in Northern European countries [9]. Since the overheating of modern lightweight prefabricated structures is an increasingly common problem on a global scale, a large number of scientific researches have recently studied it [8], [10]–[12].

European Directive on Energy Performance of Buildings (EPBD 2010/31/EU) explains that “the permissible annual cooling load required for cooling of residential buildings $Q(NC)$, calculated per unit of cooled area $A(u)$, shall not exceed 50 kWh per year per square meter area ($Q(NC)/A(u) \leq 50 \text{ kWh}/(\text{m}^2\text{a})$)” [13]. European requirements are implemented into national legislation. On the other hand, the thermal stability of a building is a direct indicator of overheating in correlation to the structural complex. Thermal stability is usually described through air temperature, as suppression factor v or phase delay η . These values are usually not defined with legislation. Slovenian guidelines and list of rules on the ventilation and air conditioning of buildings and also American and European standards define the limiting value of operative temperature during the cooling season to be 26°C [14]. Therefore, the strategy for preventing overheating in buildings depends on the building design. In order to prevent and control overheating, comprehensive measures are needed that follow the holistic principles of bioclimatic planning all the way to the introduction of passive and active building systems [15]. Phase change materials (PCM) can be used in buildings as both active or passive systems. Due to their high heat capacity they present an alternative to improve the thermal stability of a lightweight structure, as proved in many studies [16]–[20]. These studies experimentally and numerically showed that PCM reduce overheating during the entire year and improve the thermal comfort of the occupants. However, studies evaluated the performance of phase change material (PCM) on the base of single surface temperature or the air temperature. However, air temperature does not report the effect of radiant temperature and is a limited parameter within thermal comfort analyses.

This article investigates the potential of the PCM improved lightweight building envelope to be coupled with system proposed by project HERAT. This study investigates overheating in lightweight buildings from the aspect of thermal comfort and energy efficiency in cooling season. The main criterion for thermal comfort is the operative temperature (T_o) and for the energy efficiency, the energy cooling demand. According to the purpose of this research, a numerical model of a typical Slovenian single-family house with lightweight structure was modelled for three geographical locations. Furthermore, a comparative study of lightweight structure with and without PCM was done.

2. Methodology

The purpose of this research is to compare the energy efficiency and thermal comfort of lightweight structured buildings, with and without PCM, during the summer. The comfort is assessed based on air

and operative temperature. The energy efficiency was calculated based on the energy consumed for mechanical cooling (active cooling).

The chosen case was a single-family house with net floor area of 177.45 m², located in three different cities with moderate climate: Ljubljana (Slovenia), Rome (Italy) and Copenhagen (Denmark). The chosen single-family building is show in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Analysed single-family house

DesignBuilder™ software was used as a calculation tool for the determination of energy consumption (of HVAC, lighting and operation) [21]. The geometry was inserted and the simulation conditions specified as below in Table 1. Most of the data remained unchanged, unless specified otherwise.

Table 1. Simulation conditions

Fixed input data	Value
Clothing insulation	0.5 clo
CO ₂ emissions	(The amount was defined based on the function of the space)
Occupancy rate	/
Internal heat gains	/
Air leakage of all SC*	0.7 ac/h, constant
Thermal transmittance of the windows [U_w]	1.058 W/(m ² K)
Total solar energy transmittance [g]	0.579
Shading type:	blinds outside
Light gains	/
Ventilation	hybrid ventilation; (1 ACH**)
Air conditioning	The inclusion point was set when the internal air temperature exceeded 26 °C and the coefficient of cooling efficiency was 3.2
Season	Summer (1.8.-7.8.2002)***
	Whole year 2002
Location	Ljubljana (SI), Rome (IT), Copenhagen (DK)
PCM melting point (initial)****	25°C and thickness

*Structural complex (SC), **Air change per hour (ACH), ***The hottest week in 2002, for 5 days the outdoor temperature exceeded 30°C, ****Phase change materials (PCM)

Two different types of structural complexes (SC) of the building's envelope are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Lightweight wooden frame type (LW) is the lightweight SC, which bears the weight with timber elements (frame) presented in Figure 2 with characteristics. The strategies, which improve the thermal capacity characteristics, vary with the addition of PCM. The PCM is attached as a single additional layer on the inner side of the exterior wall, right before the plasterboard.

In Figure 3, the LW with PCM is presented with macro-encapsulated strategy, which was used in this study. The PCM product used within this study – additional layer of macro-encapsulated PCM (LW_{PCM}) is commercially called BioPCM™. There are several different melting points available (27°C, 25°C and 23°C) as in product abbreviations 27Q, 25Q and 23Q. Within the chosen melting point, various capacities can be chosen, namely M182, M91, M51, M27 [22]–[24].

BioPCM™ material is produced out of fatty acids and their derivatives, such as alcohols, amines and esters. Its characteristics are: latent heat (L): 210 – 250 J/g, energy storage capacity ($c_{p,e}$): 400 – 1250 kJ/m², specific heat (s): 2.2 – 4.5 J/(gK), thermal conductivity (λ): 0.15 – 2.5 W/(mK) and relative density (RD): 0.85 – 1.4 g/(mL). Table 2 shows heat transfer coefficients of both SC.

Table 2. Heat transfer coefficients U of the designed structural complexes

U	LW [W/(m ² K)]	LW _{PCM,a} [W/(m ² K)]
Exterior wall	0.139	0.130
Roof	0.111	0.111
Floor	0.260	0.260

(LW)
Lightweight
wooden frame

Figure 2. SC of the external lightweight wall with timber elements

- 1) gypsum cardboard 15 mm
- 2) polyethylene foil
- 3) wooden panel 15 mm
- 4) wooden frame with cellulose flakes 160 mm
- 5) oriented strand board (OSB) panel 15 mm
- 6) mineral wool panels
- 7) facade silicone plaster 10 mm

(LW_{PCM})
Lightweight
wooden frame
with PCM
layer

Figure 3. SC of the external lightweight wall with timber elements with macroencapsulated PCM layer

- 1) gypsum cardboard 15 mm
- *Additional layer of PCM on top of thickness of 7.4 cm (BIO PCM®)
- 2) polyethylene foil
- 3) wooden panel 15 mm
- 4) wooden frame with cellulose flakes 160 mm
- 5) oriented strand board (OSB) panel 15 mm
- 6) mineral wool panels
- 7) facade silicone plaster 10 mm

Within the simulation, the following equations were used to determine the performance of the different structural complexes. Operative temperature, T_o [°C] is determined based on [25]:

$$T_o = \frac{hc \cdot T_{ai} + hr \cdot T_r}{hc + hr} \quad (1)$$

T_{ai} (indoor air temperature) [°C], T_r (mean radiant temperature) [°C], h_c (heat-transfer coefficient by convection) [W/(m²K)] and h_r (heat-transfer coefficient by radiation) [W/(m²K)]. The T_o was used to indicate the thermal comfort. Thermal capacity of the building materials is used for determining the heat accumulation capability of the building. Thermal capacity c [J/(m³K)]:

$$C = \rho * c \quad (2)$$

ρ (density) [kg/m³], c (specific heat of the material) [J/(kgK)]. The temperature suppression factor (ν) and phase delay (η) were used to determine the building's response to the environmental temperatures (Equations 3 and 4). The temperature suppression factor is the quotient between the amplitude of the changing temperature outside and the amplitude inside. The phase delay expresses the time between the appearance of the highest temperature on the outside and the appearance of the highest temperature on the inner surface of the SC. Ideally, the phase delay is as close as possible to the time that occurs between the highest and the lowest temperatures on the outside. The ratio between ν and η should be 1. Temperature suppression factor ν [°C]:

$$\nu = \Delta T(T_{ao,max} - T_{o,max}) \quad (3)$$

ΔT (the temperature difference between $T_{ao,max}$ and $T_{o,max}$) [°C], $T_{ao,max}$ (outer air temperature daily peak) [°C] and $T_{o,max}$ (operative temperature daily peak) [°C]. Phase delay η [h]:

$$\eta = \Delta t(t_{ao,max} - t_{o,max}) \quad (4)$$

Δt (the time difference between $t_{ao,max}$ and $t_{o,max}$) [h], $t_{ao,max}$ (time value of the outer air temperature daily peak) [h] and $t_{o,max}$ (time value of the operative temperature daily peak) [h]. In this case, ν and η are calculated based on the time gap between the maximum or the minimum peak of T_{ao} and T_o . It was used to evaluate the performance of the designs – the capability of the building to delay and decrease the thermal response to the surrounding. LW was chosen as a typical representative of the lightweight wooden building where summer overheating occurs. PCM type was used as standard solution strategies to overcome summer overheating and compared with representative LW without PCM. In order to investigate the impact of different variations on the results, different variations were tested:

- LW without PCM,
- LW.PCM.a.23: M182/Q23,
- LW.PCM.a.24: M182/Q24, M91/Q24 and
- LW.PCM.a.25: M182/Q25.

The PCM layer with various melting point temperatures (23°C (PCM.a.23), 24°C (PCM.a.24), 25°C (PCM.a.25)) was investigated (variation: melting point temperature). Afterwards, the effect of capacity of PCM.a.24 was tested by decreasing the initial capacities from M182 to M91.

To evaluate the performance of the structural complexes, thermal comfort and energy consumption were analysed. The data were extracted as: outdoor air temperature [°C], inner air temperature and operative temperature [°C], delay and overheating recalculated out of T_{ai} and T_o [h] and the energy consumed for cooling the building [kWh] when T_{ai} and T_o exceeded the recommended limit. The upper and lower limits of T_{ai} and T_o were defined within Category III of indoor environment during the cooling season determined in EN15251:2007 [26]. The upper and lower limits for T_{ai} are 26°C and 23°C and for T_o 27°C and 22°C, respectively. The same limits stand when determining the electricity consumed for cooling to keep the building running within these limits. The electricity – electrical chiller is in case of thermal comfort investigations switched OFF and in case of energy efficiency investigations turned ON. The results are presented for the 1st week of August (as the week with the highest outdoor air temperatures) and for the entire year.

3. Results and discussion

The results of the analysis of overheating from the aspects of thermal comfort are presented with operative temperatures (T_o) as a basic criterion. To show the combined impact of T_{ai} and mean radiant temperature (T_{r}) on the occupant comfort during the time with overheating potential (first week of August, cooling season). The energy cooling demand is defined with [kWh/m²] needed for cooling.

Figure 4. To obtained with LW and LW PCM structure during the 1st week of Aug for Copenhagen Figure 4. show Copenhagen operating temperatures for different LW structures with and without PCM layer on the inner side of the exterior walls for three different PCM melting points (23°C, 24°C, 25°C). Additional 182 and 91 thermal capacity was analysed for 24 °C. Results for Copenhagen shows higher values of T_o in peaks for PCM 23°C compared to SC without PCM. Nevertheless, over the entire week the temperatures remained below the upper limit. The effect of PCM 25°C has higher impact on reducing T_o compared to PCM 23°C. Copenhagen has almost no difference in energy consumption with or without PCM for selected temperatures.

Figure 5. To obtained with LW and LW PCM structure during the 1st week of Aug for Ljubljana Results for Operating temperatures and cooling demand for Ljubljana is shown in Figure 5. LW with PCM 23°C, compared to LW without PCM, performed almost the same except for 4.8 at noon, which means there is small effect of T_o . The PCM 25°C has higher impact on T_o compared to PCM 23, which means that almost all temperatures during the day drop below the upper limit. The PCM at 24°C decreased the most the inner T_o and managed to keep them below the upper level for the entire week, even when its thermal capacity was split in half (M91/Q24). For Ljubljana cooling demand there is some drop in energy consumption for cooling, but not significant.

Figure 6. To obtained with LW and LW PCM structure during the 1st week of Aug for Rome

The results for Rome are shown in Figure 6. Comparing results without PCM, interestingly the PCM of 23°C shows even higher inner temperatures, because of to low melting point. The PCM 25°C decreased the inner temperatures and kept them below the upper limit. The PCM with 24°C in Rome performed with the lowest operative temperatures. When its capacity was split in half - at the end of the week the temperatures slightly increased. The increase was probably, because the outdoor temperatures were too high to accumulate the heat with lower capacity PCM 24°C. In Table 2 all results for cooling demand are presented for different LW construction with and without PCM layer.

Table 2. Cooling demand for all structures for different geographical locations

kWh/m2	LJUBLJANA		COPENHAGEN		ROME	
	1st week of Aug	Year	1st week of Aug	Year	1st week of Aug	Year
LW without PCM	1,5	52,5	1,1	48,3	1,71	56,6
M182/Q23	1,3	50,6	1,1	48,2	0,91	48,5
M182/Q24	1,2	50,2	1,0	48,2	0,91	48,5
M91/Q24	1,2	50,3	1,0	48,2	0,91	48,5
M182/Q25	1,2	50,7	1,1	48,2	0,91	48,5

Comparison of different geographical locations for better energy efficiency with the use of PCM in LW construction show that the highest reduction for cooling demand is achieved for Rome where temperatures during the summer are higher. Both, yearly and weekly energy consumption for cooling in Rome is strongly affected by the use of macro-encapsulated PCM. In Ljubljana, there is some drop in energy consumption, but not as significant as in Rome. The same as in Ljubljana, Copenhagen has almost no difference in energy consumption with or without PCM for cooling. Compared to LW, the macro-encapsulated PCM can help to reduce overheating periods in hotter climates and decrease energy consumption for cooling periods.

4. Conclusions

To prevent overheating, a holistic approach based on bioclimatic design principles is needed, where the building is adapted to climate and location characteristics [15]. Secondly, a passive PCM should be introduced to attain its maximum potential and system efficiency. Based on the study it can be concluded that:

- The presented system can increase the thermal comfort of the building and reduce the cooling demand;

- The highest overheating reduction was attained by the application of macro-encapsulated PCM with melting point of 24°C;
- In order to attain its highest efficacy, it is important to select PCM with optimum melting point temperature, since the mis-determination of the melting point cannot be corrected by the addition of thermal capacity (the melting point at 23°C has almost no effect on the performance of the lightweight structure and couldn't reduce the overheating, so different thickness should be additionally tested);
- The combinations of PCM with multi-layers of different melting points may also be applied in order to cover different temperature ranges;
- Macro-encapsulated strategy has the potential to increase the capacity, decrease the overheating periods and decrease cooling demand;
- The system is highly applicable for the renovation of existing lightweight buildings or geometrically complex structures, by not losing the delicate amount of the floor area in the building.
- The system may be combined with the one proposed by project HEART as it helps to overcome the summer periods with high cooling demand. However, it should be noted that prior to the coupling the PCM in the building envelope needs to be optimized to avoid unnecessary heating or cooling demand.

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6. References

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